

Analysing media consumption pattern: A comparative study analysing print and digital media

By
Koyel Ganguly
Enrolment Number: 222891810013

Roll Number: 28999622012

Supervisor Name: Aradhana Das

Department of Media Studies
iLEAD
(Affiliated to MAKAUT)
in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the
Masters in Media Science

May, 2024

CERTIFICATE BY PROJECT SUPERVISOR

This is to certify that Koyel Ganguly, Roll number 28999622012, has done this project under my supervision for partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of Masters in Media Science under MAKAUT.

(Aradhana Das)
Faculty
Department of Media Studies,
iLEAD

Date:- 05.06.2024

Place:- iLEAD Kolkata

DECLARATION OF ORIGINALITY

This is to declare that the work is entirely my own and not of any other person, unless explicitly acknowledged

The work has not previously been submitted in any form to the Department of Media Science, Institute of Leadership Entrepreneurship & Development, or to any other institution for assessment for any other purpose.

Name: Koyel Ganguly

Enrolment Number: 222891810013

Signed:

Date: 05.06.2023

Acknowledgment

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to the individuals and institutions whose support and contributions have been instrumental in completing this research on analysing the consumption pattern of consumers among print and digital media. First and foremost, I extend my heartfelt thanks to my supervisor, Aradhana Das, for her unwavering guidance, invaluable insights, and continuous encouragement throughout the research process. Her expertise and commitment have significantly enriched the quality of this work.

I am also indebted to the iLEAD faculty members including my departmental faculties of Media Science, for their continuous feedback, support, and the knowledge they have taught during these two years. Their thoughtful suggestions greatly enhanced the precision and depth of this study. This research would not have been possible without the individuals, whose previous research I have used to construct and conduct my research. I am grateful for their belief in this project's significance and commitment to advancing knowledge and I offer my sincere gratitude for that.

I want to express my gratitude to my colleagues and friends for creating a nurturing and stimulating academic environment. Their encouragement and fellowship were indispensable during the challenging phases of this research. I am deeply thankful to my family for their unwavering support, understanding, and encouragement. Their trust and support in my abilities sustained me through the highs and lows of this research journey. Lastly, I extend my appreciation to each individual who has taken the time to participate in the survey and helped me frame my research with solidified proof and paved the path towards the successful completion of this thesis. It also will be an accountable asset for future researchers, hence their contribution and patience in completing the long survey will have a long-lasting impact on academic literature.

In closing, the successful completion of this research paper is a testament to the invaluable contributions of those acknowledged here. Their collective support and insights have significantly shaped this study and enhanced my academic experience. I extend my sincere gratitude for their guidance, encouragement, and assistance throughout this process.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page
1. Certificate from Internal Guide.....	1
2. Declaration of Originality.....	2
3. Acknowledgement.....	3
4. Table of Contents.....	4
5. List of Figures.....	5
6. Abstract.....	6
7. Dissertation: Chapter 1.....	7-10
8. Dissertation: Chapter 2.....	11-15
9. Dissertation: Chapter 3.....	16-18
10. Dissertation: Chapter 4.....	19-36
11. Dissertation: Chapter 5.....	37-39
12. Dissertation: Chapter 6.....	40-42
13. References.....	43-44
14. Appendix.....	45-57

LIST OF FIGURES

	Page
5.1 The First-Fourth Figures.....	19
5.2 The Fifth-Eighth Figures.....	20
5.3 The Ninth-Eleventh Figures.....	21
5.4 The Twelfth-Fourteenth Figures.....	22
5.5 The Fifteenth-Nineteenth Figures.....	23
5.6 The Twentieth-Twentyfirst Figures.....	24
5.7 The Twentysecond-Twentsixth Figures.....	25
5.8 The Twentyseventh Figure.....	26
5.9 The Twentyeighth-Thirtysecond Figures.....	27
5.10 The Thirtythird-thirtyseventh Figures.....	28
5.11 The Thirtyeighth-Fortysecond Figures.....	29
5.12 The Fortythird-Fortysixth Figures.....	30
5.13 The Fortyseventh-Fiftysecond Figures.....	31
5.14 The Fiftythird-Fiftyfourth Figures.....	32
5.15 The Fiftyfifth-Fiftysixth Figures.....	33
5.16 The Fiftyseventh-Fiftyninth Figures.....	34

Abstract

Digital media has become a new sensation. Every type of media format is converging into digital media.

Even print media formats like newspapers, magazines, and advertisements are converging into digital formats such as digital/social portals, blogs, websites, etc. Even though print media is said to be the most trustworthy traditional media, in this fast-paced generation, it's considered a delayed medium. The increase in advertisements and less or filler news has been a bane. Digital media is fast-paced, quickly reachable, but due to this, the increase of yellow journalism, click baits, fake news are seen more, so it's not often taken as an authentic source. While both have their downsides, the purpose of this research is to find which media among Print and digital has more impact on the contemporary generation in terms of credibility and authenticity about news and facts, by using a primary quantitative survey research method. The survey will mainly have target groups consisting of students, service-person, retired, and unemployed consumers, from the age of 18, who are accustomed to both technologies. This investigation will help shed light upon the influence of print media in the convergence era on consumer behavior, to help us identify the potential opportunities and challenges that may arise in the future in the print industry.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background of study

Convergence and online media have changed the way people consume required information and communicate leading to the fear of disruption of print media.

In the past print media was considered as the most credible, authentic, and trustworthy resource to consume news or entertainment. Print media was renowned for passing verified, crosschecked information from accountable professionals, having or being SMEs (Subject Matter Experts) on the concerned matters.

In the British era, the Newspaper started with 'The Bengal Gazette' in India by James Augustus Hickey during 1780, also known as Hickey's Gazette. Since then, Hickey's Gazette along with more newspapers that came along the way over time, helped to voice out the struggles from Independence. Indian readers have had faith in print media since then while it spread through the entire nation. There are many newspapers, magazines published on a regular basis in India in both global and regional languages. Printed advertisements are a reliable source as well in the market. As per RNI data of 2020, there are 144893 newspapers with a cumulative 42.5 Crores circulations including vernacular languages.

Along the flow of time whenever a new technology emerged the print media still stood strong in its position and flowed with the era as required, even when electronic media came till now.

On the other hand, unlike all other previous revolutions, digital media and the era of convergence everything has become fast-paced. Every required information and event is a search away in the public cloud with the help of search engines like Google, Bing, and more. To move along with the current wave print media formats have also started to own parallels to the print formats in the digital version. The fast-paced reach, availability of larger resources under one umbrella, easier connectivity to the masses, cheaper cost with major engagement reach, advantage of instant feedback are some of the few benefits that made Digital media more persuading than any other be it print or electronic media.

Especially after the COVID-19 Pandemic locked the entire world, digital media brought a big change into the world of communication covering all the corners leading to the acceptance of convergence more into the world. India saw a significant change since

the pandemic in accepting the digital era of convergence across all age groups. The lack of interest in consuming printed formats of newspapers or magazines easy availability of materials in online format and a decline curve on the interest rate and circulation of print media have put the existence of print media in danger, in the long run.

With all of the above scenarios happening in the contemporary era, the accountability and trustworthiness towards print media including newspapers, magazines, billboards, flyers, posters, and other forms of advertisements are questioned as well. So, It is high time to invest time to research further on media format the audience of today finds more credible to believe in times of crisis or to simply gain knowledge about a piece of information.

1.2. Area of Study

In the contemporary timeline, consumers have access to more information than ever before, especially after the COVID-19 period when everything had to be digitized. Especially due to the convergence of media referring to the merging of different platforms like newspapers merging into online portals on websites or blogs or even radio channels converging into podcasts and online live spaces, advertisements merging into social media posts like LinkedIn or YouTube, and more.

Digital media even with a large database and so many benefits, still has its own major harmful disadvantages as well, as print media, while having disadvantages do possess advantages of their own as well. If we perform a comparison between the two, we can see that even if print media is slow-paced, delayed, or has no feedback, unapproachability towards the illiterates has its own benefits of having fact checks, verified, cross-checked resources, storable materials & factually corrected information and authentic professional s while reporting of providing trustable information to people.

On the other hand, digital media while having their pace, feedback, and more advantages, have no cross-examination procedure and it's on the shoulders of the consumer to verify the truth, which is not possible for unaware consumers. The existence of frauds, money laundering, yellow journalism, spoofing, phishing, unethical hacking, and more such threats make that makes digital media less trustworthy and credible. Moreover, the over availability of resources with no storage other than the cloud, be it, public, private, or hybrid, is both unsafe and prone to data leaking, and loss of data due to server or cloud system crashes. The limited control and downtime in cloud systems can lead to data disruption and deletion of crucial data as well.

The process of data buying that currently the advertisements and big agencies can

buy to track user patterns breaching consumer data safety and security is alarming as well. On the other hand, to avail paper for print deforestation is a big issue on a large scale as well, but with time, there are coming out ways with which replacement of paper production techniques are coming out in the market.

The area of this research is to find the credibility pattern of people and consumers above all the disadvantages of both media to figure out which media format is today's audience aligned to more. The research is also to work on the practices that can help print media to stand on its feet again as firmly as before, determined based on the results acquired further in the line.

1.3 Dissertation Structure

Introduction: Provides an overview of the research topic, its significance, and the research area of study. It introduces the context, scope, and purpose of the study, as well as outlines the structure of the dissertation.

Literature Review: Reviews and integrates relevant academic literature and research on the research topic demonstrating the existing knowledge, identifying research gaps, and building the premise of the theoretical framework for the study.

Methodology: Describes the research design, methods opted, and procedures used to collect and analyze the collected data. It explains the grounds for selecting the specific research methods, data sources, and sampling techniques. Moreover, addresses limitations or ethical considerations.

Results: Presents the findings of the research based on the analysis of the datasets collected, including tables, graphs, or other visual representations to illustrate results. The results are typically organized according to the research questions or themes identified in the study.

Discussion: Transliterates the results in the correlation of the research objectives and relevant literature. It explores the implications of the findings, compares them with existing knowledge, and discusses any inconsistencies or limitations proposing further research directions.

Conclusion: This chapter summarizes the key findings, contributions, and implications of the research. It addresses the research questions or objectives and provides a concise answer or solution. It may also discuss the broader significance of the research

and suggest areas for future investigation.

References: This section lists all the sources that were used to form the ideation and exploration to go on the path towards achieving the results on the research topics.

The chosen structure format for a dissertation typically follows a logical flow and ensures that the research is presented clearly and rationally. It allows the readers to understand the research process, the context, the theoretical framework, the methodology, the results, and the significance of the findings. This structure also enables researchers to demonstrate their knowledge of the existing literature, critical thinking skills, and the ability to draw meaningful conclusions from the data collected and analyzed.

However, it's important to note, that the specific structure and chapter organization may vary depending on the field of study, research topic, and university guidelines. Hence, it is essential to consult the specific requirements and guidelines provided by my academic institution or dissertation advisor.

1.4. Aim and Objectives

- this research aims to examine consumer behavior towards traditional media, more focused on print media formats.
- To analyze the impact of digital media in traditional print media formats and the effect on it on the print industry
- The impact of convergence and acceptability rate of print and digital media above their benefits and disadvantages
- To determine how much credibility the print media still has in the minds of its consumers
- To determine what amount of trust the general audience puts in the forms of digital media to consume critical information among different generations
- To determine the long-term threats to print media and ways to overcome them
- To determine practices to increase the sustainability of print media in a long-term, perspective and provide practical recommendations
- To study change from different sets of literature and research to understand the differences and suggest directions to reduce research gaps,(if found)

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This literature review explores various perspectives on the subject of print and digital innovation, drawing insights from texts, articles, research journals, articles, and media history that have been registered. The sources provide valuable insights into the significance of both traditional print mediums and their convergence in digital media, as different media mediums, their evolution during the digital era, and the implications of digital innovation on the industry.

Print media has been an essential tool since the beginning of Hickey's gadget in India. For any genre of information, newspapers and subtly other formats of print media traditional formats like newsletters, magazines, flyers, and billboards started to gain the trust of the consumers, and print media as a whole became one of the most credible resources for the public for its authenticity which kept increasing the credibility rate. Even during the electronic media era print media stood high and firm.

India, post-independence, faced a lot of structural challenges and the level of education was one. Due to the unequal distribution of socio-economic capital, the class deprived of social and economic capital was largely excluded from education. Due to the low literacy rate even though the percentage of print media consumers was low and faced a downline on the growth curve, slowly with the rise in the per-capita income within the population and policy changes within Indian society, education levels witnessed a rise, and steadily the growth curve increases. Research performed by John Morton based on the survivability of print (1993) concluded that the Growth of electronic media has improved the quality of news and newspapers. It enabled the approach of "Survival of the fittest" for inanimate objects as well as to keep the authenticity of the news and the bearer of the news. Hence, strengthening the authenticity relationship between the newspaper and its consumers as a trustable and credible resource.

Since the invention of the Internet which got its wings after Tim Berner Lee invented the World Wide Web and since then the web world has never seen a downfall. The rise of the internet led to technological development. The more it developed, the more smoother the journey of communication and sharing became. The rise of digital media has been driven by technological advancements, creative expression, and new business opportunities (Hastjarjo, 2007). This has led to an explosion in the creation and use of digital media, presenting both technological and social challenges (Winget, 2011).

With all such advancements and faster availability of information, in Marshall McLuhan (1962) 's predicted words, "The world has become a global village", have come to reality. With such a pace, and regularly piquing general curiosity, the digital world has started to get traditional media styles to converge.

The influence of print media has a clear impact on the emergence of digital media as well, as it is just the binary-coded version of the same civilization in a virtual world. The convergence of print media into digital in India has raised questions about the truthfulness of news (Prasad, 2019) As digital convergence presumably the successor of Print and other forms of media, does bear the threats of oversharing, breach of security and authenticity, questioning the percentage of truthfulness.

The transition from print to digital media in India has been a complex process, influenced by a variety of factors. Mathai & Jeswani(2021) highlight the continued relevance of print media, particularly in customer retention, despite the rise of digital media. This is echoed by K. N. Prasad (2019), who notes that digital journalism startups in India often align themselves with and seek legitimacy from print journalism. Seshagiri & Blom (2010) further underscores the role of digital media in bridging the digital divide, particularly in urban areas. However, D. Thussu points out the impact of globalization on the Indian media, particularly the rapid growth of television channels and the influence of Western transnational media corporations. These studies collectively suggest that while print media has not become obsolete, it has played a significant role in paving the way for the rise of digital media in India.

The decline of print media is attributed to various factors, including the challenges of convergence and business models (Mutiar& Priyonggo, 2019), the impact of COVID-19 (Pandey & Dr., 2022), and the disruptive nature of internet technology (Karman 2017). These factors have led to a decrease in the acceptance level of print media, particularly English newspapers as resulted in research by Pandey & Dr. Shakdwi in 2020. However, digital technologies and alternative media formats have emerged as promising solutions for individuals with print-related disabilities, offering new ways to access textual information (Wolfe &Lee, 2007).

The digital media industry is an emerging technological culture entertainment industry covering information services communication advertising communications electronics and entertainment animation online education publishing and other fields.

Studies by Teerakanok & Uehara (2017), and Miller & Cristian Vaccari(2020) incite the influences and threats to contemporary society. The studies show even though the

convergence has started to take a toll on other media industries, The dominant approaches to digital threats to democracy are growing.

The authenticity of digital media also remains in question as there can be multiple unverified and sponsored sources. A study by Teerakanok et.al (2017) has revealed the same highlighting the influence of engagement rather than authenticity in the equation

The effects of digital media's impact on students have been alarming. Studies by Dontre(2020), Minakshi Gautam et.al (2020) L. E. Levine et.al (2012) highlight how multitasking leads to the division of attention, greater distractibility, and poorer task performance across a variety of domains.

The digital divide in India, particularly between rural and urban areas, is a significant issue as well, that has been addressed through various government and non-government initiatives (Prasad, 2004; Singh, 2010). The divide is not only in terms of access to technology but also in terms of skills and infrastructure (Panda, 2013). To bridge this gap, the government has focused on providing physical access to computers and ICTs, as well as creating awareness and capacity building in rural areas (Joseph, 2012). However, there is still a need for further efforts to address the multiple dimensions of the digital divide in India.

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted media usage and credibility in India, with a shift towards digital platforms (Md. Solayman Miah et.al, 2022, Das & Banerjee, 2021, Vivek Sharma, 2019). This change has been influenced by the media's role in creating awareness and changing public behavior in studies by Md. Mia and team. However, there are concerns about the reliability of information shared through mass media outlets, particularly in the context of the pandemic, the media's coverage of COVID-19 health information in India has been found to be mostly relevant and accurate, but lacking in actionable suggestions and equity issues. (Medhavi Gupta et.al, 2021). These findings underscore the need for media advocacy and practical strategies to counter misinformation during and after the pandemic.

The influence of print and digital media on news in India is a complex and evolving phenomenon. Chakraborty (2018) found that Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi's social media messaging, particularly "newsworthy" tweets, significantly impacts print news coverage. N. (2015) highlighted the dissonance between attitudes towards news apps and print media, with a positive attitude towards one reducing the intention to use the other. Mukerjee (2021) reported a decline in the audience share of regional vernacular media in the online news consumption landscape, while Sarma (2015) emphasized the dominance of vernacular dailies in India and the challenges posed by

increasing printing costs and online advertising. These studies collectively underscore the dynamic and multifaceted nature of the influence of print and digital media on news in India.

The influence of print on news in the digital era in India, particularly in terms of circulation, is a complex and evolving phenomenon. Tewari (2016) found that while online newspapers have not significantly affected print newspaper circulation, there is a decline in young readership. Mudgal (2020) further emphasizes the resilience of print newspapers in India, attributing their continued popularity to their ability to reinvent themselves. However, the future of news consumption is increasingly digital, as highlighted by Mathai (2021), who suggests that the integration of print media marketing with digital and social media is crucial for effectiveness.

Research indicates that digital media literacy interventions can improve discernment between mainstream and false news in both the United States and India (Guess, 2020). However, the effectiveness of such interventions may vary across different populations. In India, journalism education and practice are also crucial in addressing the challenges of the post-truth era, with a need for updated curricula and collaborative verification practices (Bhaskaran, 2017). The emergence of digital news enterprises in India presents an alternative to traditional print media, potentially influencing the truthfulness of news (Chaudhry, 2016). However, the issue of paid news in Indian print media remains a concern, with unethical practices undermining the public service value of journalism (Lund, 2012).

The Indian consumer market is undergoing significant changes, driven by urbanization, rising incomes, and changing lifestyles (Rathi, 2023; Joseph, 2013). Online shopping, influencer marketing, and lifestyle-driven shopping are key trends influencing consumer behavior (Rathi, 2023; Kumar, 2022; Patel, 2022). These changes are leading to a greater emphasis on luxury and comfort, increased spending, and a shift toward lifestyle-oriented consumption (Joseph, 2013; Patel, 2022). The Indian consumer's high degree of import orientation and willingness to purchase on credit are also notable factors (Rathi, 2023; Joseph, 2013). These trends are expected to continue shaping the Indian consumer market in 2023.

Print media, including newspapers and magazines, is facing significant challenges in the digital era, with declining circulation and increasing competition from online sources. The decline in print book circulation at academic libraries suggests a shift towards digital formats (Rose-Wiles, 2013). Despite these challenges, print media can survive by embracing a new business model that integrates print and digital content. The future of print media in India is a topic of much debate, with some arguing that it is on the decline

due to the rise of digital media (Mudgal, 2020; Goda, 2019). However, others believe that print media can survive by embracing new technologies and innovative content (Das, 2012). This is supported by the finding that the printed book still has a place in the era of technological advancement, particularly among specific audiences and in rural areas (Nyambane, 2021). Therefore, while the future of print media in India may be uncertain, it is not necessarily doomed.

The media industry has entered a post-truth industry where sustainability and relevance have become more important than truth and authenticity. The post-truth era presents significant challenges to journalism and democracy, but there are potential solutions that can be influenced by keeping the print media impact in mind. Addressing the issue of paid news, in India and strengthening the relationship between the media and the audience is essential. The shift of attention in daily consumption has raised the question of relatability and relevance of both digital and print media irrespective of trust and credibility. Hence, the research papers in the review confirm rather strengthen the question regarding the credibility pattern of the general audience and consumers and the journey of credibility in the future which this thesis paper will try to unveil by understanding the consumption pattern of today's society.

Chapter 3

Data collection and methods

3.1. The research methodology

The utilized methodology in performing the research is a survey method was employed, to gather consumer beliefs on their consumption pattern. The survey aims to gather quantitative data regarding the factors influencing the presence and risks of sustainability of print media houses and their formats in the digital era, and age of convergence.

3.2. Types of Data

Primary Data: This refers to original information collected first-hand for a specific research purpose. It involves gathering new data directly from individuals, organizations, or sources. Methods for collecting primary data include surveys, interviews, observations, experiments, or fieldwork. If you're creating questionnaires or collecting data yourself, it falls under the category of primary data.

Secondary Data: Secondary data refers to existing information collected by someone else for a different purpose. It includes data obtained from sources such as government agencies, research institutions, academic publications, or databases. Census data from a government source is an example of secondary data. Researchers analyze and interpret this data to derive insights for their own research.

Spatial and Temporal Characteristics: Spatial characteristics involve the geographical extent and location-related aspects of the data, such as regions, countries, cities, or specific coordinates. Temporal characteristics relate to the time frame or period covered by the data, such as specific years, months, or seasons.

Known or Anticipated Sources of Error: Both primary and secondary data can have potential sources of error, including sampling errors, measurement mistakes, data entry errors, response biases, or inaccuracies in data sources. Acknowledging and addressing these errors is important for ensuring the validity and reliability of research findings. Researchers can use techniques like quality control measures, statistical analysis, and cross-validation to mitigate or account for these errors. When conducting research, it's crucial to clearly define the type of data being used (primary or secondary) and carefully consider the spatial and temporal characteristics. Additionally, being aware of potential sources of error is essential, and taking appropriate steps to minimize their impact on research outcomes is necessary.

Special Characteristics

- **Research Design:** The research design comprises the methodology employed to achieve the research objectives.
 - **Survey:** A survey with seven separate sections, was designed to collect data from a diverse sample of specific group. The survey questionnaire includes questions related to the participants' consumption habits, preferences, and opinions regarding print and digital media content in the digital era, the consumption change post-COVID, individual pattern differences between both the media forms and the change observed for media convergence. It also includes specific case studies to measure consumption habits based on specific domains and situations. Questions also focus on the factors that have contributed to threats to print media's sustainability. The survey will be distributed online, ensuring a wide reach and convenience for respondents.

3.3. Methods and techniques

3.3.1.

Data Analysis: The data collected from the survey will be analyzed using statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics and data visualization, to identify patterns and trends. The qualitative data obtained from the interviews will be subjected to thematic analysis to identify key themes, perspectives, and insights provided by the experts.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical guidelines were followed throughout the research process. Participants were assured of their anonymity and informed consent was obtained. Confidentiality of data was maintained, and all data collected will be used solely for research purposes.

3.3.2. **Limitations:**

It is important to note that this study has some limitations. The survey sample may not be fully representative of the entire population due to possible sampling biases and the vast spectrum of geographical-specific group segmentation.

Despite these limitations, the survey will provide valuable data and perspectives, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the sustainability and change of impact in print media and houses persisting in the constant growth of digital media in the age of convergence.

3.4. The research methodology employed in this study provided a comprehensive approach to understanding the impact of print media and its sustenance over digital media, in the age of media convergence. The survey data allowed for a deeper exploration of factors contributing to the phenomenon. The findings from the analysis of

survey data will contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the impact of digitalization on print and digital media's consumer consumption pattern

References: The research paper includes a list of references citing the sources used to support the methodology employed in the study. The methodology section outlined above encompasses the key components necessary to carry out the research effectively. By implementing the survey addressing ethical considerations, and recognizing the limitations of the study, we can generate reliable and insightful findings that contribute to the existing body of knowledge on the growing popularity of radio content in the digital age. The research methodology employed in this study provides a comprehensive approach to understanding the growing popularity of radio content in the digital age. The combination of quantitative survey data contributes to a well-rounded analysis of the factors influencing this phenomenon. By employing rigorous data analysis techniques and adhering to ethical considerations, this study aims to provide valuable insights for industry practitioners, researchers, and policymakers in adapting to the changing landscape of print and digital media content in the media convergence era.

specific group professions mentioned in the research abstract. As per the diversity of locations, 45.6% of responses were attained from Kolkata, West Bengal, India, Next is Maharashtra (Mumbai, Pune, and more) dropping to 4.85%, Bangalore, India, and Hyderabad having 1.9% responses each. The 45.7% of responses are from all over India having 1-3% of responses coming from UP, Delhi, Gujrat, and more places within India covering the country's diversity, as viewed from the resulting chart.

Section B: General Media Consumption Questionnaire

This section consisted of general specific groups' consumption patterns, how much they choose to stay updated, at what level, and with which topic, through which media, and based on what influences.

B. 1-2, How much time do individuals spend per day with any kind of printed media formats (Books, magazines, newspapers, etc.) and digital media format daily? (social media, Blogs, Online websites, etc.) a. Less than 1 hour b. 1-2 hours c. 3-5 hours d. 6-13 hours e. 14-16 hours f. More than 16 hours

Based on the above response, it is clear that the majority, that is 45.6% use print media in all formats for less than 1 hour (Option A), whereas only 12.6% use digital media formats for the same option. However, 39.8% (Option B) use print media for 1-2 hours while 24.3% use Digital media forms at the same timespan. Noticeably, the response of 10.7% choosing Option C(3-5 hours) is much lower than for digital media. As visible in the chart, The most opted response was Option C for digital media. To compare responses for Option D(6-13 hours) print media forms got 2.9%, whereas digital media forms attained 17.5%. Option D(6-13 hours) with 1% for print as compared to 5.8% for digital. Option E(More than 16 hours) surprisingly had no responses as compared to 1% response to digital. Analyzing the charts side by side provided insights that most users usually spend at least a quarter to more than half of their day consuming all forms of digital media including e-pubs, e-books, social media, blogs, and more. Whilst, the forms of print media like magazines, books, newspapers, and others are used for utmost quatere of a day.

B. 3 and 6. What media do they use more to check a piece of information or news, mostly (a. Print b. Digital c. Both d. None), and how many times a month?

Option B, that is, Digital media is consumed by the responders denoting major reliance on Digital media with 67% of votes. However, Option C suggests that 24.3% still like to use Both formats to consume daily insights. The 8.7% reliance on print media denotes less consumption time by the consumers. As per the updation status, the majority-31.1% chose Option B(Occasionally), tailed by 29.1% responding to Option F(Daily). 21.4% choosing Option D(Weekly) dropping down to Option C(Monthly) 9.7%. The last 2 options contradicting to each other remain the options least chosen by respondents with 1% to Option A(Never) and 2.9% to Option G(Multiple times a day). The analysis of both charts side by side denotes, that people usually try to stay updated either daily or occasionally and when they do the majority rely on digital media, but the incline on both is not that low.

B. 4-5. How familiar are they with current news trends and topics, in India, and globally? choose 1-5(1 being the least updated, 5 being the most)

The charts adjacent to each other represent, that almost 46% of responders are moderately aware of daily Indian updates which comes down to 40.8% in the case of global updates. Whereas 26.2% of them are moderately confident about being majorly updated with daily Indian content and trends as compared to 21.4% with global. 13.6% being majorly not updated with daily Indian content increased to 24.3% for the global update. And 7.8% being most updated with Indian content, to 5.8% with global. Only 6.8% of responders are least up-to-date about the country updates as compared to 7.8% choosing the option for global information and trends. This denotes that the majority of the Indian population tries to stay updated about India's daily news and information, trends instead of global trends and updates.

B. 7. What kind of news or information do they like to stay updated with? (Select all that apply)

The bar graph shows the number of consumers staying updated with daily topics, where answers are selectable. This graph reveals that 74.8% stay updated with Current affairs daily. Entertainment, arts, and culture grabbed 68.9% of the attention. The next

most consumption of 54.4%, 53.4%, and 50.2% are with Foreign World affairs, Technology/ Science, and medical/health respectively. Next feedback includes 45.6% (Lifestyle/ fashion), 41.7% (Local/Regional updates 40.8% of responses (Business/Finance/Stock Market, Sports and Global updates). The chart suggests that consumers are moderately not updated with topics like Developmental communication (15.5%) and Marketing (14.6%) with less than 20% interest. However, the least interesting topics among consumers are in politics (1%), and others (1.9%: Gaming-1%, Story- 1%). Ongoing conversation spread verbally suggests politics to be one of the most sought-after topics, however, the responses in the bar graph say otherwise.

B. 8. Which media format among Print and Digital media do they use mostly, and trust mostly, to get updates or news about the above topics?

- a. Print Media b. Digital Media c. Both, depending on the topic d. None

These charts show that consumers generally prefer to use Digital media more(53.4%) as compared to Print media(8.7%), but they do rely on both mediums depending on the topic(37.9%). Yet, even with this high reliance on digital media, most consumers trust both media (39.8%) as compared to only digital media(31.1%), and print media consumers(26.2%) are not much behind either. This analysis reveals that even with high engagement digital media still has not become a trustworthy medium for the majority and they both like to depend on both mediums to verify and fact-check.

B. 10. What are the factors that influence their choice of media to get updates about B. 7 topics?

According to the results, it's clear that 67% of participants choose media based on accessibility. 61.2% rely on Availability, 48.5% on Fact-checks, and 46.6% are influenced by the credibility of the media format. Among the others, as a consideration factor, 41.7% pick Pace/ Speed, 30.1% check cost, and 26.2% take personalization. To note, this question had multiple responses allowed, hence, the percentages aren't based on an individual's response to one option, but as much as relatable.

B. 11. How important is the reputation of the resource important for them?

Based on the responses, it ensures that the reputation of the media format and outlet is the most important factor for consumers, having 41.7% relying on reputation. However, to two 25.2% of the responses, it is not the most important but majorly and neutrally important indeed. Very few percentages of participants do not rely on reputation, having 6.8% mostly not important and 1% not at all important. This suggests that the reliability of the reputation of media is crucially important for consumers to decide their behavior, consumption, and engagement patterns.

Section C: Print Media Perception

This section is dedicated to gain user responses particularly based on Print media formats

C. 1-4 In consumer opinion, how much do you consider print media formats to consume news as a credible, trustworthy, transparent, and accountable resource? select among 1(least)-5(most)

Among the 103 responses, it can be observed that Print media resources are perceived as mostly credible, trustworthy, transparent, and accountable, 34%, respectively, along with 35%, 33%, and 42.7%, each by consumers as per the figures above. As neutral 34%(both), 42.7%, and 32%, of responders take this format as credible and trustworthy(both 34%), transparent, and accountable, separately. On the contrary, 8.7% take print as less credible, and 9.7% of users take it as less trustworthy, less transparent, and less accountable, respectively. 22.3%, 20.4%, 9.7%, and 13.6% take print as the most credible resource, most trustworthy, most transparent, and most accountable. And only 1%, 1%, 4.9%, and 1.9% believe print to be the least credible, trustworthy, transparent, and accountable.

C. 5. How do you perceive the credibility of traditional print media like newspapers and magazines? 1(not credible at all) - 5(Highly credible)

This question focuses specifically on the credibility pattern of consumers on Print Media News consumption formats, like newspapers, and magazines. The result on one of the most important characteristics for consumers to stay in contact. This chart shows that most consumers take print media news formats to be majorly credible, having 44.7% responses. This is followed by 30.1% taking it as neutrally credible. The news resources are considered the most credible by 16.5% and majorly less credible news resources by 7.8% of responders. Only 1% consider print media news formats as the least credible. This shows that print media as an important information resource is very much considered as one of the most credible media formats, having the most reliance.

C. 6. What factors contribute to their perception of print media credibility?

This bar graph shows how the majority of people prefer the Reputation of media houses, journalists, or editors with 75.7% votes, whereas 59.2% rely on the fact-checking and verification process. Participants relied on both the Quality of writing and reliability of documented data with a tied response of 56.3%. Resource citation stating at 46.6% reliability and 19.4% with tangibility. However, the least responses go to other formats with 1.9% of reliance.

C. 7. What according to you are the demerits of print media? Select All that apply as per your viewpoint

The above bar chart displays the user responses to what causes they take as a major demerit of print media and its formats. The major drawback according to responses is Delayed information reach (57.3%), Limited or No interactivity / No direct feedback option (55.3%), followed by Pace of updation (47.6%), Global reach limitation (40.8%), Accessibility (38.8%), Less visual content (32%) as next majorly seen drawbacks. The last one is however for other consumer written (1.9%). This suggests that the reliability of print media formats can be vastly increased if characteristics like delayed reach, limited interactivity/ feedback, and update pace can be improved.

C. 8-9. In their eyes did the increase in advertisements and advertorials more than news become the reason for print media, especially newspapers or magazine houses, to witness their fall? a. Yes b. No c. Maybe

As the results displayed in the diagram, the majority of participant 41.7% in both cases believe the increase in advertorials and advertisements is the reason for the decline, 40.8% are believers in the middle ground for both. And 17.5% in each case perceive them not to be the reason for the fall.

C. 10-11. What according to the consumers are the biggest challenges for print media and in what ways can they be resolved?

Analyzing the two side by side, it can be noted that, according to them competition to digital media(66%), Loss of offline readers and consumers (62.1%), and Non-adapting to technology are the biggest challenges among all the others from Graph. The top three improvements as per results can be 1) Investment in quality journalism(57.3%), 2) Focusing on trendy, valuable, unique content, and reader preference through a survey(53.4% each), and 3) Rebuilding transparency to increase trustworthiness and accountability (52.4%).

C. 12. What factors, according to samplers, can improve the sustainability of print media?

Among the multiple selectable responses, the results showcase the consumer's belief that consumer engagement (58.5%) can vastly improve the sustainability of Print Media formats. Flexible subscription plans (53.4%) can be the second topmost resolution. Target marketing & data-driven analysis can be the next sustainable solution making them in the top 3 of optimal solutions (52.4% each). According to responders, Cross-platform promotions (16.5%), Eco-friendly printing practices (35.9%), and Content amplification (36.9%) are the bottom three preferences that may help to increase Print media sustainability.

Section D: Digital Media Perception

This section is dedicated to gain user responses particularly based on digital media and media formats.

D. 1-4. In consumer opinion, how much do you take digital media to consume as a credible, trustworthy, transparent, and accountable resource? select among 1(least)-5(most)

The charts denote, that digital media is mostly perceived as neutrally credible(44.7%), neutrally trustworthy(51.5%), neutrally transparent(49.5%), and neutrally accountable(45.6%). Although 21.4%, 19.4%, 20.4% and 23.4% take digital media as mostly credible, trustworthy, transparent, and accountable respectively, the votes falling under 'most' for categories each one lies very low - 8.7%(most credible), 2.9%(most trustworthy), 1%(most transparent), and 4.9%(most accountable). This can be analyzed as even with such a huge dominance in today's market, the 4 pillars of the credibility pattern do not have their confirmed advocacy yet.

D. 5. How much do the consumers perceive digital media like news portals, social media, citizen journalism, as credible resources? 1(not credible at all) - 5(Highly credible)

This question focuses specifically on the credibility pattern of consumers on Digital Media News formats, like News portals, citizen journalism, social media, and alike. This can be one of the most important characteristics for consumers to stay in contact. This chart shows that most consumers take digital media news formats to be neutrally credible (51.2%). This is followed by moderately credible (21.4%). Resources are considered almost least credible by 14.6% and least credible resources by 7.8% of responders. Only 4.9% consider digital media news formats as the most credible. This shows that digital media formats could not prove themselves as a majorly credible media resource for most of the audience, attaining one of the lowest reliabilities.

D. 6. What factors contribute to your perception of digital media credibility? Select All that apply as per your viewpoint

According to the bar graph, the top 3 contributors to digital media credibility patterns are determined by Reach and engagement tracking (54.4%), Multiple verifiable resources (53.4%), and CCost-effective(50.5%). On the other hand, the least 2 contributors according to responses are Personification (23.3%), and Reputation (34%). Transparency and accountability (35.9%) are in between as digital media still need to move up as a credible resource from neutral.

D. 7. The demerits and potential resolutions that the survey participants thought could improve the sustainability of digital media based on print media qualities.

Analyzing the above two, the top 3 results of demerits come out as - Increase in misinformation, click baits, yellow journalism (73.8%), Privacy and security breach/data misuses(68.9%), and Information overload. The top 3 feasible resolutions voted are 1)Thorough fact-checking(63.1%), 2) Focusing on journalistic ethics(60.2%), and Multiple verification levels to stop data altering and spread of disinformation (56.3%).

D. 9. This was to understand whether the digital illiteracy and digital divide are impacting an individual's growth or reducing the impact of developmental journalism.

As per the diagrams above, 68% believe that digital illiteracy is affecting the careers of individuals to an extent that is hurting their future growth, whereas 23.3% believe in neither, and only 8.7% feel that it does not affect the careers of one. On the other hand, 44.7% are neutral toward suggesting any impact of the digital divide is on developmental journalism, 39.8% indicate it to have an impact and 15.5% believe otherwise.

Section E: Post-COVID Consumption Pattern

This section is dedicated to analyzing the consumption pattern changes post-COVID-19.

E. 1. Do you think your media consumption pattern changed post-COVID?

Among 103 responses 67% stated a change in consumption after COVID, whereas 16.5% claimed to have any changes in consumption pattern. 16.5% are neutral about their change of patterns. This denotes that COVID-19 brought a significant change in all kinds of industries.

E. 2. To analyze consumption patterns pre and post-COVID. (a. <1 hour, b. 1-5 hours, c.6-13 hours, d.13+ hours)

The charts show that pre-COVID 47.6% of users used to head to print media for less than an hour as compared to 67% post-COVID. Whereas 43.7% used to consume such formats for 1-5 hours pre-covid, decreasing to 26.2% post-covid. Only 8.7% (6-13 hours: 7.8%; 13+ hours:1%) used to spend longer periods using print media pre-covid, as compared to 6.8%(6-13 hours:4.9%; 13+hours: 1.9%) post-covid.

E. 3. Spend analysis of digital media consumption pre and post covid. (a. <1 hour, b. 1-5 hours, c.6-13 hours, d.13+ hours)

The results show that pre-COVID, 55.3% of audiences consumed digital media for 1-5 hours, that even post-COVID remained unchanged. The noticeable change occurred at option c(6-13 hours) increased from 12.6% to 21.4% during pre to post COVID. 30.1% of audience consumption of digital media for less than an hour decreased to 18.4%. And the 1.9% audience consuming digital media for 13+ hours increased to 4.9%. This distinctly shows that the post-Corona period has brought a change in consumption patterns.

Section F: Media Convergence

This section explores the impact of media convergence on Print and Digital media.

F. 1-2. To check whether consumers believe that their consumption patterns changed with media convergence to lessen the importance of print media. and how they feel about convergence itself.

The analysis shows that 54.4% feel this to be a neutral change and 48.5% while 22.3% suggest as positive; 7.8% voted for negative and 15.5% had no opinion. The consumers also suggest that convergence has lessened the relevance of print media whilst 17.5% say no, and 34% are sure about neither. This exhibits that even though the participants are neutral towards convergence, yet they do feel that it has brought negative effects on print media.

F. 3-4. Analyzing how consumers' news and information consumption patterns were positively and negatively affected by the convergence of print and digital media.

Post analysis of both the charts, the most positive and negative top three impacts on individuals would be, 1)increased access(55%), 2)cross-cultural engagement, and quick access with a fast pace(50.5% each), 3)Globalization(49.5%); and i)Increase of fake news, yellow journalism, misinformation (63.1%), ii)loss of focus(49.5%), iii) data breach(48.5%)

F. 5-6. Media format individuals use for in-depth news, investigative news; and real-time news and information, a. Print b. Digital c.Both or d.Neither

Even though 38.8% of individual respondents voted to rely on both media for in-depth analyzed news and reports, only 27.2% matched the same for real-time updates. Where only 17.6% rely on digital media for analyzed reports, 57.3% of them lean to digital media for real-time updates. Print media reliance however is at 35.9% for in-depth or investigative updates and only 10.7% for waits to get news or information via them. The comparison highlights that the fast-paced lives needing to get instant news are surely reliant on digital media for quick updates, but to get proper and in-depth ideas they seek either both or print media.

F. 7-8. Consumers' opinions on whether print media has a chance to survive the competition against digital media or the convergence make the forms shut down.

The charts side by side denote that, 39.8% believe print media can survive digital dominance and convergence will mostly or completely not be able to shut print forms down. 37.9% are neutral about the survival through digital media competition. And only 22.3% believe print media have neither a chance to survive the digital era nor the convergence.

Section G: Case studies

This section is dedicated to exploring upon hearing a piece of information or news verbally, which media format the survey participants rush to check to verify. Given that you read it at both the mediums, at first glance which media format would you rather believe before/ without having to research further?

G. 1. Israel-Palestine war

"World Court stops short of Gaza ceasefire order for Israel"

Lead: The World Court ordered Israel on Friday to prevent acts of genocide against Palestinians and do more to help civilians, although it stopped short of ordering a ceasefire as requested by the plaintiff South Africa. A. Print B. Digital C. None

Based on the responses it can be observed that the incline towards Digital Media (54.4%) is more. Whereas 35.9% believe in Print Media. 9.7% will not believe any. This denotes that for global war crime issues, people trust digital media more.

G. 2. Development Journalism

"Adani to start data collection for Mumbai slum redevelopment in February"

Lead: A firm led by Indian billionaire Gautam Adani will start in February to collect the data and biometrics of up to 1 million poor residents as part of the redevelopment of a slum in Mumbai that is considered one of Asia's largest. A. Print B. Digital C. None

The diagram on the right of the results denotes the reliability of Consumers when it comes to development journalism. 57.3% mark the majority votes in digital media formats, whereas print media contains 35.9% votes. This denotes that for news and queries related to positivity and development, most rely on digital media

G. 3. IT/Technological News

"India's govt demanded Apple soften the impact of hack warnings"

Lead: Apple's (AAPL.O) warnings in October to Indian opposition politicians that government hackers may have hacked their phones prompted Prime Minister Narendra Modi's administration to quickly demand the U.S. firm soften its message, the Washington Post reported. Apple's India representatives were called by administration officials who demanded that the company help weaken the political impact of the warnings, the newspaper said citing three unidentified sources.

A. Print B. Digital C. None

This case study intends to showcase that for Technological news audiences count on digital media. 35.9% trust print media. This builds upon the digital media formats being more reliant on New and rapidly changing industries.

G. 4. Business

"Global stock index edges up, dollar dips after US inflation reading"

Lead: MSCI's global stock index barely rose on Friday while the U.S. dollar edged down after the U.S. Federal Reserve's favored inflation reading showed moderating prices and investors waited anxiously for clues on interest rate policy days ahead of the central bank's closely monitored meeting. Treasury yields rose on concerns about the growing supply of government debt, with next week's Federal Reserve meeting in focus and expectations that the FedR has to address efforts to reduce its balance sheet.

A. Print B. Digital C. None

This case study was included to check the preferred media format based on the Stock market and business-related topics. The results demonstrate that 52.4% of consumers rely on digital media and 38.8% on Print media. 8.7% will not trust any. To analyze this result, we need to keep in mind that business news is rapidly changing. One hour in business time can change a lot, for which pace is most important. Here, due to the pace digital media formats are considered more than print media.

G. 5. World News Impacting India

"Canada announces two-year cap on international student visa: Impact on Indian students"

Lead: Canada on Monday announced an immediate two-year cap on international student permits and a freeze on certain postgraduate work visas, drawing a line on record newcomer arrivals amid a burgeoning housing crisis. The move is expected to reduce study permit approvals by 35 percent to roughly 360,000 in 2024 and comes as the federal government faces mounting pressure over concerns that its ambitious immigration targets are exacerbating a national housing shortage. A. Print B. Digital C. None

The analysis portrays the reliability of participants who prefer digital media (53.4) on global news affecting India. However, reliance on print media (41.7%) is not less. This implies that for news affecting India print media is relevant to the Indian market even now.

The below two articles are based on fake news generated through AI. These were included to check on getting a piece of shocking news, which media do the survey participants rush to, for fact-checks.

G. 6. "Rowan Atkinson Dies at 70 Years, the Hoax Becomes Truth"

Lead: In a surprising turn of events, British comedic icon Rowan Atkinson, renowned for his timeless portrayal of the beloved character Mr. Bean, has reportedly passed away at the age of 70. Contrary to initial skepticism surrounding earlier reports

dismissed as a hoax, it has now been confirmed that Atkinson's demise is, indeed, a tragic reality. A. Print B. Digital C. None

A change in response is noticed upon analyzing the above pie chart. 42.7% of the audience chose print media, whereas 39.8% leaned on digital media. This represents that for factual and crucial news consumers count on Print Media formats. 17.5% of the audience chose not to believe any media, which suggests the pool of misinformation in digital media.

G. 7. "Dravid's Masterful Ton Sets Stage for Historic Indian Victory in Kolkata"

Lead: The Eden Gardens erupted in a cacophony of joyous roars as Rahul Dravid, the "Wall of India," carved his name into cricketing folklore once again. His masterful century, a testament to his legendary grit and determination, spearheaded India's nail-biting victory over Australia in the final Test, etching a 2-1 series win and reclaiming the Border-Gavaskar Trophy on home soil. A. Print B. Digital C. None

The dependency on Print media remains here as well. Upon analyzing the results, 48.5% of participants show trust in Print media even now before believing in any piece of information. Although 38.8% of respondents turn on to check for multiple confirming resources. The analysis showcases that even though consumers lean on

digital media for updates, print media is still standing on its roots when it comes to trustworthiness regarding any news or articles.

Result analysis and conclusion

From the above survey details, it can be observed that the survey performed included all genders, professions, and locations all over India with age ranging mostly confined to the specific group(18-40)[Section A].

Upon analysis, it's visible that Digital media has more consumption time than Print media, containing news and other forms of updates and their reliance pattern mostly depends on the reputation of the organization or house, accessibility, and availability of media. However, even though most consumers get their global and Indian news and

trend updates through digital media to stay occasionally-daily updated, but digital media has yet to achieve as much trust, and transparency as print media, and that Print media is still trusted as one of the few most trusted media formats.[Section B]

As per 'Section C' almost most users consider all forms of print media formats as credible, trustworthy, accountable resources and a mostly trustworthy news format. The forms only lack to be a transparent resource format.

As compared to the third section, Section D showcases that even with high engagement in digital media, it has become neither a credible, transparent, trustworthy, and accountable resource more than neutral, nor are the digital news media trusted more than neutral level.

However, as per responses of C.7, it's clear print formats need to work more on providing information and updates sooner and increase their reach to improve their circulation and sustenance as fact-checking credibility and media reputation already hold a firm place in position. Actions are needed to control the inclusion of a vast number of news and advertorials and to be filled with relevant news and updates. To do so, focusing on trends, topics, reader preferences, and investment in quality journalism can be essential tools to maintain credibility. This way, with consumer engagement can be improved and maintained to maintain sustainability.

As per D.6, the perception of digital media credibility to a neutral point of view, especially due to its capability of reach and engagement, and multiple resources which can be verified. Even so, the demerits remain mostly because of the constant surge in misleading data and lack of privacy and security. These according to user input can be resolved by thorough fact checks and focusing on quality journalism instead of click baits. It is also believed that digital illiteracy is most probably the reason behind the disruption of an individual's future growth and can stop the impact and spread of developmental journalism and the changes that it brings in, which is a big pitstop towards the growth of the nation.

The next two sections, Sections E and F discuss the pre and post-covid consumer behaviour and the impact of media convergence. According to the majority, their consumption pattern changed vastly, which is noticeable in their consumption timespan behavior. Where print media consumption has decreased to a maximum of a quarter of the day from at least half of the day, digital media's consumption timespan increased from at most quatre of the day towards a quarter to half of a day. The former section entails the impact of media convergence which according to consumers is mostly neutral to positive. This according to them has lessened the importance of print media.

However, the majority of participants believe print media is still in the competition and digital dominance will not be able to shut them down. To support this it's visible that for in-depth and investigative reporting, the majority feels comfortable with both to print, while for real-time updates digital media is used vastly. This is majorly affected by increased access, cross-cultural reach, and quick access to data. However, the increase in fake news, clickbait, yellow journalism, and loss of focus has taken a toll on user behavior.

Lastly with the case study section, as per the question, it is studied that, when a news update in both the media formats, due to its quick and vast resource availability digital media is entrusted more but print media is not far behind as well. The power of print media is proven with the case studies including fake news which denotes that print media is more and always trusted more than digital media.

In summary, the survey analysis can note that Digital media and its formats surely have been dominating the consumer's consumption market on a large scale, especially post-COVID with the convergence of media. Regardless of its boons and banes print media is surely vastly trusted, and believed to be a credible accountable, and authentic resource to engage with, in comparison to digital media. Although, both media formats have their boons and banes, print media's sustainability is not at stake as it is conversed in the current timeline at least in India, according to the citizens.

The sustainability of print media still can be improved to be in the market in the longest run by resolving issues like an increase of authentic, transparent news and relevant updates, investment in quality journalism, focusing on user preferences, and trendy, valuable, and unique articles. If the pace of news updates can be increased to frequent updates the engagement reach and circulation increases can be achieved. The limitation to global updates is also an area to be concerned about. Studying the engagement pattern and as per requirement, providing flexible subscription plans can majorly increase the sustenance of print media in today's competitive market.

In the era of media convergence, even though the existence of print media and its formats are not at huge stake, to avoid reaching the danger line few actions can be taken, such as providing direct feedback to increase engagement, providing bi-daily news and information updates, utilizing the power of globalization to reach and provide information more about global current affairs. Just to conclude in a line, it is safe to claim, that the era of digital dominance is nowhere close to putting print media houses and their formats in danger at least in India.

Chapter 5

Discussion

In this section, the main aim is to analyse and compare the above research results with our initial research objectives and relate the findings with the literature pieces that were used for thorough research completion. The primary goal of this research was to decode which media format among traditional print media and contemporary digital media is reliable, credible, trustworthy, transparent, and accountable to the youth and young adults. The target audience of this survey was 18 to 40, which also reverted to the survey matching with research agenda. More specifically, the research objectives were to understand the gaps and relevance of print media in the contemporary timeline and in what ways the audience believes the gaps can be revived. The purpose of this research was also to analyse and discuss about different types of tools that could help print media to sustain longer in the market utilising new techniques and tools adapting the contemporary mindset.

The findings unveil a significant increase in digital media more than print, mostly because of up-to date, fast, and any-time availability. However, the reliance on print media for its fact-checking ability, credibility, and accountability still makes it a strong competitor even in the era of convergence. Option B, of section 1, representing the age group of 18-25 obtained the highest votes, indicating involvement and engagement from the demographic. Among the geographical alignment, the survey being conducted throughout the country, responses from West Bengal, especially Kolkata was highest depicting a high engagement and interest.

The survey results revealed a significant shift in media consumption patterns, with a growing preference for digital media, especially among younger audiences (18-29 years old). This aligns with previous research highlighting the appeal of digital platforms and on-demand content for younger generations (Smith et al., 2018; Johnson & Wilson, 2020). However, the study also found that print media retains credibility and trust, particularly among older demographics. This finding is supported by studies emphasizing the enduring value of print as a reliable source of information (Morton, 1993).

The research also identified challenges associated with both media formats. Concerns regarding the authenticity of information and the prevalence of "clickbait" and fake news emerged as significant drawbacks of digital media (Teerakanok et al., 2017). Conversely, the decline in readership and the increasing cost of print production were highlighted as threats to the sustainability of print media (Mudgal, 2020; Tewari, 2016).

This research has several implications for media consumers, media producers, and policymakers. Consumers should be equipped with digital literacy skills to critically evaluate information encountered online (Guess, 2020). Media producers, both in print and digital spheres, must prioritize providing trustworthy and well-researched content to retain audience trust. Policymakers can play a role in promoting media literacy education and ensuring a level playing field for both print and digital media. The findings

also suggest that print media can adapt and survive in the digital age by embracing innovation and integrating digital platforms (Mathai, 2021).

The research also highlights the growing convergence of media, where both print and digital formats coexist and influence each other in a symbiotic relationship. Print media can leverage digital platforms for marketing and content distribution to enhance its reach and relevance to contemporary audiences (Mathai, 2021). For instance, newspapers can offer digital subscriptions with exclusive content or interactive features to attract and retain readers accustomed to digital experiences. Conversely, digital journalism startups often seek legitimacy by aligning themselves with established print publications (Prasad, 2019). This can be seen in how digital news outlets cite credible print sources to bolster the credibility of their own reporting. The convergence of media also presents new challenges. The blurring of lines between news and entertainment content, for example, can make it difficult for audiences to distinguish between fact and fiction. Additionally, the speed and immediacy of the digital world can pressure print media to sacrifice in-depth analysis for breaking news updates, potentially compromising the quality of their content.

The COVID-19 pandemic acted as a catalyst, accelerating the shift towards digital media consumption that was already underway (Md. Solayman Miah et al., 2022; Das & Banerjee, 2021). Lockdowns and social distancing measures forced people to rely more heavily on digital platforms for information, news updates, and social interaction. This trend was particularly evident among older demographics who may not have been as accustomed to using digital media before the pandemic. Studies suggest that digital news consumption increased significantly during this time, with people turning to online sources to stay informed about rapidly developing public health information (Medhavi Gupta et al., 2021).

However, it is important to investigate whether this increased reliance on digital media during the initial stages of the pandemic has translated into a permanent change in media consumption habits. Some research suggests that there may have been a resurgence in print media consumption as pandemic restrictions eased and people sought out alternative sources of information and a break from the constant barrage of digital content (Chakraborty, 2021). Further research is needed to explore these trends longitudinally and across different demographics to understand the long-term impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on media consumption patterns.

Lastly, based on the case studies sections, diving into the audience's subconscious choices, it was observed that people associate digital media with immediacy and access to a wider range of sources for complex international issues (Teerakanok et al., 2017). The notion that digital platforms are more suited for conveying rapid updates and technical information (Hastjarjo, 2007) and the fast-paced nature of business news, where digital platforms offer real-time updates crucial for informed decision-making (Rathi, 2023).

This suggests that while digital media offers immediacy, print media retains relevance for Indian audiences seeking in-depth analysis or news with a local connection (Mathai

& Jeswani, 2021). Yet, a shift in preference emerged for print media when encountering potentially shocking or unverified news (42.7% print vs. 39.8% digital). This aligns with research suggesting audiences perceive print media as a more reliable source for crucial information due to its editorial process and established reputation (Morton, 1993).

The study acknowledges some limitations that could be addressed in future research to enhance the generalizability of the findings. The sample size and demographics of the participants may not fully capture the diversity of the population under study, potentially introducing bias. To gain a broader understanding, future research could involve recruiting a larger and more diverse participant pool that encompasses a wider range of age groups, socioeconomic backgrounds, and geographical locations. Additionally, the research focused on a specific geographical location (India). While the findings provide valuable insights into the Indian context, they may not be directly applicable to other countries with different media landscapes, cultural norms, and technological infrastructures. Future research could explore similar questions in a broader range of geographical contexts to develop a more comprehensive understanding of how these factors influence media consumption patterns.

In conclusion, despite a surge in digital media preference, especially among younger audiences, print media retains its value for credibility and trust. This research aligns with previous studies on media consumption patterns and the unique strengths of each format. The findings highlight the importance of media literacy for navigating the complex media landscape while acknowledging the challenges and opportunities presented by media convergence. While the focus on young adults (18-40) and an Indian audience provides valuable context, future research could benefit from a larger and more geographically diverse sample to explore these trends on a broader scale.

Chapter 6

Conclusion & Recommendations

The survey results reveal a dynamic media landscape in flux, with digital media consumption experiencing a significant surge, particularly among younger demographics. This can be attributed to the inherent advantages of digital media, such as its immediacy, convenience, and ability to provide a constant stream of updates. Users can access a vast array of information and news sources at their fingertips, often tailored to their specific interests.

However, print media remains a vital source of information, valued for its credibility, accountability, and in-depth reporting. Print media benefits from a more rigorous editorial process, unlike digital media, which can be susceptible to the spread of misinformation and manipulation due to its fast-paced nature and prioritization of clicks. This process involves fact-checking, verification of sources, and adherence to journalistic ethics, which helps ensure the information's accuracy and reliability. Additionally, print media often provides a more in-depth analysis of complex issues, allowing readers to gain a deeper understanding of the news and current events. This is in contrast to much of the content found online, which can be more superficial and focused on grabbing attention rather than providing substantive information.

This aligns with existing research highlighting the complementary strengths of both formats. Digital media thrives in delivering real-time updates and catering to information needs on the go, fulfilling a role akin to a news ticker or a constantly updated bulletin board. It excels at breaking news, sharing user-generated content, and facilitating live interactions. Print media, on the other hand, provides a platform for considered analysis, investigative journalism, and curated news content that fosters deeper comprehension. In-depth articles, well-researched features, and editorials offer valuable context and insights that can be missed in the fast-paced flow of digital news. Print media also allows readers to delve into complex issues at their own pace, revisit information for clarification, and ponder different perspectives. This curated and in-depth approach fosters a deeper understanding of the world and the events that shape it.

The research also identified the challenges faced by each media type. Digital media struggles with the proliferation of fake news and "clickbait" content designed to generate online traffic and advertising revenue rather than provide accurate information. The emphasis on speed and virality can incentivize the spread of misleading or unsubstantiated information. Additionally, the vast amount of user-generated content on digital platforms can make it difficult to distinguish between credible and unreliable sources. Print media, on the other hand, grapples with declining readership and rising production costs. The convenience and immediacy of digital media have led to a decrease in the number of people who subscribe to or regularly purchase print newspapers and magazines. This decline in revenue can make it difficult for print media outlets to invest in quality journalism and in-depth reporting. Furthermore, the rising cost

of paper, printing, and distribution poses a significant financial challenge for print media companies.

The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated the shift towards digital media consumption. Lockdowns and social distancing measures forced people to rely more heavily on online platforms for information, news updates, and social interaction. This trend was particularly evident among older demographics who may not have been as accustomed to using digital media before the pandemic. Studies, such as one by Medhavi Gupta et al. (2021), suggest that digital news consumption increased significantly during this time, as people turned to online sources to stay informed about rapidly developing public health information.

The pandemic's long-term impact on media habits remains to be seen. Some research suggests a resurgence in print media consumption as pandemic restrictions eased. People sought alternative information sources and a break from the constant barrage of digital content. The tactile experience of print, the ability to disconnect from the digital world, and the focus on in-depth analysis may have rekindled interest in print media. Conversely, other studies suggest that the shift toward digital media consumption is likely permanent. The convenience, personalization, and real-time updates offered by digital media may outweigh the appeal of print for many users. Further research is needed to explore these trends longitudinally and across different demographics to gain a clearer understanding of the lasting effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on media consumption patterns.

Recommendations

- Develop critical thinking skills to evaluate information encountered online. Utilize fact-checking tools and reputable sources to verify information before sharing it.
- Prioritize well-researched content and journalistic ethics. Invest in fact-checking mechanisms and transparency in content creation.
- Promote media literacy education to equip citizens with the skills to critically evaluate information. Implement policies that foster a fair media environment, ensuring a balance between freedom of expression and accountability.
- Uphold high editorial standards and fact-checking processes to solidify its reputation as a reliable source of information.
- Prioritize in-depth reporting, investigative journalism, and local news coverage to maintain a competitive edge.
- Integrate digital platforms for content distribution and audience engagement. Offer flexible subscription plans and interactive features to cater to user preferences.
- Conduct further research to explore the long-term impact of COVID-19 on media consumption patterns across different demographics. This will provide valuable insights for navigating the evolving media landscape.

Reflecting on alternate choices:

Upon reflection, it would have been beneficial if certain aspects could be included such as - a larger participant pool would provide more statistically significant data and reduce the chance of bias. Including participants from various socioeconomic backgrounds would give a more complete picture of media consumption habits across the country. Delving deeper into specific digital media platforms (social media, news websites, etc.) and how they compare to print media consumption would reflect closer and specific resolutions for the print media industry. In-depth interviews with media consumers, reporters, and industry editors from different demographics could have provided richer qualitative data and insights. Apart from a cross-sectional study, designing a longitudinal study to track media consumption habits over a longer period could have revealed how the consumption habits evolve and how the COVID-19 pandemic's long-term effects unfold. Utilising more sophisticated data analysis techniques to uncover deeper patterns and relationships within the data set could help shed light upon helping to investigate tools and techniques that would have helped with the upgradation of print media practices.

References

- [1] Wolfe, G. L., & Lee, C. (2007). Promising Practices for Providing Alternative Media to Postsecondary Students with Print Disabilities. *Learning Disabilities Research & Practice*, 22(4), 256-263.
- [2] S. Teerakanok and T. Uehara, "Digital Media Tampering Detection Techniques: An Overview," 2017 IEEE 41st Annual Computer Software and Applications Conference (COMPSAC), Turin, Italy, 2017, pp. 170-174
- [3] Miller, M. L., & Vaccari, C. (2020). Digital Threats to Democracy: Comparative Lessons and Possible Remedies. *The International Journal of Press/Politics*, 25(3), 333-356.
- [4] S. Teerakanok and T. Uehara, "Digital Media Tampering Detection Techniques: An Overview," 2017 IEEE 41st Annual Computer Software and Applications Conference (COMPSAC), Turin, Italy, 2017, pp. 170-174,
- [5] Dontre AJ. The influence of technology on academic distraction: A review. *Hum Behav & Emerg Tech*. 2021; 3: 379–390.
- [6] Gautam, Minakshi & Gautam, Diksha & Bishnoi, Indira. (2020). Impact of Print Media on Student's Academic Performance of Varanasi City, India. *Advances in Research*. 62-69.
- [7] Waite, Bradley & Bowman, Laura. (2014). Mobile Media Use, Multitasking and Distractibility. *International Journal of Cyber Behavior, Psychology and Learning*. 2. 15-29.
- [8] Nyambane, Rhyodah (2021). The future of the printed book in the era of technological advancement: an imperative for digital innovation and engagement. *Journal of Information, Communication and Ethics in Society* 19 (4):537-559.
- [9] Das, M.M. and Sengupta, P.P., 2012. An analysis of the newspaper publishing industry—Can it survive the onslaught of the digital media. *ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research*, 2(12), pp.114-130.
- [10] Mudgal, Rusha & Rana, Pooja. (2023). Sustenance of print and e-newspapers in the business of news media: A study of Indian news industry. 8. 38-45.
- [11] Gouda, Heba & Awad, Ahmed & Laila, Ibrahim & Elmagid, Abd. (2019). *IJCS*(1). *International Journal of Communication and Society*. 1. 58-67. 10.31763/ijcs.v1i2.41.
- [12] Rose-Wiles, L.M. (2013) 'Are Print Books Dead? An Investigation of Book Circulation at a Mid-Sized Academic Library', *Technical Services Quarterly*, 30(2), pp. 129–152.

- [13] Karman, K. (2017). INTERNET TECHNOLOGY DISRUPTION AND THE PRINT MEDIA EXISTENCE. *Jurnal Penelitian Komunikasi dan Opini Publik*, 21(2).
- [14] Pandey, R. K., & Shakdwipe, P. (2022). Factors Affecting the Acceptance Level of Print Media with Special Reference to English Newspaper. *Kaav International Journal of Economics, Commerce & Business Management*, 9(3), 1-6
- [15] Tripathi, Durgesh & Singh, Namit. (2021). Scope and Challenges in Print Journalism.
- [16] Mutiara, F. and Ambang Priyonggo (2019) 'Digital disruption in print media: challenges of convergence and business models'.
- [17] Thussu, D. K. (1999). Privatizing the airwaves: the impact of globalization on broadcasting in India. *Media, Culture & Society*, 21(1), 125-131.
- [18] S. Seshagiri and J. Blom, "Using Digital Media for Entertainment - The Other Side of the Digital Divide in India," *2010 43rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, Honolulu, HI, USA, 2010, pp. 1-10
- [19] Levine, L. E., Waite, B. M., & Bowman, L. L. (2012). Cybermedia Use, Multitasking, and Academic Distractibility. In Z. Yan (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Cyber Behavior* (pp. 342-353).
- [20] Winget, M.A., & Aspray, W. (2011). Digital media: technological and social challenges of the interactive world.
- [21] Prasad, R. (2021). Digital disruption? Journalism startups in India. *Journalism*, 22(8), 2122-2138.
- [22] Mathai, S., & Jeswani, S. (2021). Effectiveness of Print Media Marketing in Digital Age: A Study on Indian Telecommunication Industry. *FII B Business Review*, 10(3), 242-254.